

Optical Resolution and Reactions of ($\pm$)-*p*-Ethoxybenzhydrol

K. A. Thaker

Optically active ester of *p*-ethoxybenzhydrol reacts with racemisation. When the hydrogen phthalate of this carbinol is hydrolysed by dilute aqueous alkali, racemisation occurs, but optical activity is maintained on hydrolysis by concentrated alkali in ethanolic solution or with sodium ethoxide. From an aqueous solution of sodium salt of hydrogen phthalate, the neutral ester separates; in presence of sodium *p*-toluenesulphonate, the sodium salt is converted into sulphone. Like *p*-methoxybenzhydrol¹, this alcohol also undergoes a remarkable phenomenon of alkyl-oxygen fission.

The carboxylic esters of methyl phenyl methanol², methyl α -naphthyl methanol³, and *p*-methoxybenzhydrol react by alkyl-oxygen mechanism, showing the electron-releasing properties of phenyl, α -naphthyl, and *p*-methoxy radicals. Assuming that *p*-ethoxy radical should also exhibit a similar phenomenon, the effect of hydrolysis of hydrogen phthalate of *p*-ethoxybenzhydrol has been undertaken. The optical resolution of the ($\pm$)-*p*-ethoxybenzhydrol has been studied by fractional crystallisations of the quinidine salt of its hydrogen phthalate and the tendency of this carbinol and its hydrogen phthalate towards alkyl-oxygen fission has been studied by the usual methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Ethoxybenzophenone.—To a mixture of benzyl chloride (141.0 g.) and phenetole (122.0 g.) in CS₂ (500 ml) was slowly added portionwise anhydrous aluminium chloride (200 g., 1.5 *M*). The mixture was stirred vigorously and kept overnight. On completion of the reaction, the orange-coloured compound was filtered, washed with CS₂ and then with light petroleum (40-60°), and added to a mixture of HCl (conc., 100 ml) and ice. The dark red oil separating was extracted with ether, the extract was successively washed with NaOH solution and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). On evaporation of the solvent the distillate was collected under reduced pressure (180-90°/5 mm). The product on solidification afforded pale orange plates (123 g.), m.p. 40-45°. It was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid as colorless plates, m.p. 46-47° (Heilbron's Dictionary records m.p. 39°). (Found: C, 79.7; H, 6.3. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄O₂: C, 79.6; H, 6.2%).

($\pm$)-*p*-Ethoxybenzhydrol.—The above ketone (72.3 g.) in ethanol (730 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hrs. with NaOH (73 g.) and zinc dust (73 g.). The solution after removal of zinc dust was poured in HCl (conc., 100 ml) and ice. The white compound separating was filtered and dried; yield 71%, m.p. 40-41°. (Found: C, 79.27; H, 6.5. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₆O₂: C, 79.47; H, 7.0%).

1. Balfé *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 805.
2. Downer and Kenyon, *ibid.*, 1939, 1156.
3. Balfé *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, 798.

(±)-*Hydrogen Phthalate of the Benzhydrol*.—A mixture of the above carbinol (22.6 g.), benzene (50 ml), pyridine (8.2 g.), and phthalic anhydride (14.8 g.) was warmed to form a homogeneous liquid and allowed to stand at room temperature for 72 hrs. Acetone was then added to the mixture and the product was taken in ether (50 ml) with 3*N*-HCl and ice. The ethereal extract was washed successively with HCl and water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent provided a white solid (23 g.), which was crystallised from ether/light petroleum, m.p. 105-108°. (Found by rapid titration with 0.1*N*-HCl: M.W., 372.7. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires M.W., 376).

Sulphone from (±)-p-Ethoxybenzhydrol.—(±)-*p*-Ethoxybenzhydrol (0.68 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml) was added to sodium *p*-toluenesulphinate (0.71 g.) in acetic acid (4 ml) to which a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.) were added. After 24 hrs. a white crystalline substance (0.74 g.) separated; m.p. 157-62°. It was recrystallised from butanol¹⁸ as small colorless rods, m.p. 164-65°. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 5.8; S, 8.3. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 72.1; H, 6.0; S, 8.7%).

Sulphone from (±)-p-Ethoxybenzhydryl Hydrogen Phthalate.—To the H. P. of *p*-ethoxybenzhydrol (1.83 g.), dissolved in 3*N*-NaOH (18 ml), was added an aqueous solution of *p*-toluenesulphinate (1.07 g. in 20 ml). At the end of about 12 minutes, a slight cloudy solution began to appear which was allowed to stand overnight. The sulphone was filtered, washed, and dried (1.58 g.); m.p. 158-62°. The mixed m.p. of the crystallised sulphone from the (±)-carbinol and the one prepared from (±)-hydrogen phthalate was 164°.

p-Ethoxybenzhydryl Chloride.—*p*-Ethoxybenzhydrol (1 g.) was triturated with acetyl chloride (1 ml) and after about 30 seconds, the yellow-green cloudy solution became amber-coloured; the product was kept in a desiccator over NaOH for several days. The colour of the liquid changed to pale yellow; b.p. 131-32°/0.2 mm; n_D^{17} 1.5912. Attempts to solidify this failed. (Found: Cl, 13.6. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{OCl}$ requires Cl, 14.3%).

p-Ethoxybenzhydrylamine and its Derivatives.—*p*-Ethoxybenzhydryl hydrogen phthalate (5 g.) was dissolved in ammonium hydroxide (50 ml) and the mixture allowed to stand at room temperature for one week, when a colorless oil separated. The liquid separating was decanted and washed with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with NaOH and water and dried over potassium carbonate. On evaporation of the ether, a gummy mass (1.14 g.) was obtained which did not crystallise. It was further used for preparation of acetyl and benzoyl derivatives.

Benzoyl Derivative.—The gum (0.87 g.) from above was shaken with benzoyl chloride (1 ml) and 3*N*-NaOH solution (5 ml). The gummy solid so obtained was dissolved in ethanol from which a crystalline product, m.p. 145-146°, was obtained. (Found: N, 4.48. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 4.23%).

Acetyl Derivative.—The gum from above (0.27 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride for 10 mins. On pouring the mixture on water, an oil separated which soon solidified (0.30 g.). It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 135-36°.

Di-(p-ethoxybenzhydryl)phthalate.—*p*-Ethoxybenzhydryl hydrogen phthalate (3.76 g.) was dissolved in 15*N*-NaOH solution when a turbidity developed after a few minutes. On keeping the mixture overnight, a gummy mass separated. This was removed, taken in ether, washed with water, and the ethereal extract on drying and evaporation

afforded a white mass which was crystallised from methanol (1.2 g.), m.p. 105-106°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 5.72. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$: C, 77.82; H, 5.84%).

Optical Resolution of ($\pm$)-p-Ethoxybenzhydryl Hydrogen Phthalate.—Quinidine (19.6 g.) was added to ($\pm$)-H.P. (22.5 g.) in acetone (70 ml) when on keeping the contents overnight, the less soluble quinidine salt separated. This was filtered and dried (24.5 g.); m.p. 102-103°. Three recrystallisations of the crop from acetone afforded optically active (–)-hydrogen phthalate of the carbinol, when decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.); m.p. 94°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -14.1^\circ$ (c, 4.5 in chloroform). (Found by rapid titration with 0.1N-NaOH: M.W., 373. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires M.W., 376).

The optical rotation of the hydrogen phthalate rapidly dropped and after several hours, it was found to be -2.3° and on keeping overnight, it completely racemised in chloroform solution, indicating dismutation.

The specific rotations of (–)-ethoxybenzhydrylhydrogen phthalate in other solvents were also recorded (Table I).

TABLE I

$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	c.	Solvent.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	c.	Solvent.
-15.6°	3.5	EtOH	-19.3°	4.5	CS_2
-15.8°	3.5	MeOH	-9.2°	3.4	Dioxan
-8.2°	4.2	Benzene	-1.3°	5.2	Pyridine
-0.3°	3.8	CS_2			

(–)-*p*-Ethoxybenzhydryl.—The active (–)-*p*-ethoxybenzhydryl hydrogen phthalate (4 g.) was refluxed with ethanol (20 ml) and sodium (1.5 g). The contents were cooled and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the washed and dried ethereal extract yielded the active carbinol as a viscous oil which did not solidify on keeping in the refrigerator for 5 to 6 weeks. $[\alpha]_D^{25} -8.2^\circ$ (c, 3.6 in ethanol); $[\alpha]_D^{25} -8.3^\circ$ (c, 3.6 in methanol); $[\alpha]_D^{25} -2.1^\circ$ (c, 3.8 in chloroform) $[\alpha]_D^{25} -2.8^\circ$ (c, 3.2 in benzene). (Found: C, 80.1; H, 6.35. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$: C, 79.47; H, 7.0%).

(+)-Hydrogen Phthalate of *p*-Ethoxybenzhydryl.—The more soluble quinidine salt from the filtrate on slight concentration and decomposition by H_2SO_4 (dil.) furnished partially active (+)-hydrogen phthalate; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.6^\circ$ (c, 3.6 in chloroform), m.p. 72-74°.

(+)-*p*-Ethoxybenzhydryl.—The partially active (+)-*p*-ethoxybenzhydryl hydrogen phthalate (8.0 g.) was refluxed with ethanol (40 ml) and sodium slices (8 g.) for 2 hrs. and the contents of the flask were cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract on washing, drying, and evaporation gave the viscous oil having $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.2^\circ$.

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